

**THE INFLUENCE OF THE DEMONSTRATION METHOD
ON THE LEARNING MOTIVATION OF CLASS VI
STUDENTS OF SDN 078553 ORLIN, SOUTH NIAS
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Abstract: The demonstration method is very important in teaching because it makes abstract concepts more concrete and easier for students to understand. In addition, demonstrations involve students directly in the learning process. They can see, hear, and often participate in demonstrations, which helps improve information retention. Meanwhile, motivating students is one of the most important aspects of effective teaching. This research aims to determine the effect of the demonstration method on the learning motivation of class VI students at SDN 078553 Orlin in Indonesian language subjects. The method used in this research is a qualitative descriptive method. The sample in the research was class VI, 32 people. Data collection techniques are interviews, observation and documentation. The results of the research conducted provide information that the demonstration method is very efficient in helping to shape students' characters such as cooperation, responsibility, caring, tolerance and is able to increase students' learning motivation. The demonstration method is never separated from the teacher's control to monitor the development of learning outcomes so that it can have a positive influence.

Keywords: Demonstration Method, Learning Motivation, Teacher's Role.

This is an open-access article under the [CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license**Introduction**

The world of education has entered an era of globalization, where the climate of competition has penetrated every educational institution. In the current competitive climate, it is very difficult for an educational institution to survive well if it does not have the ability to adapt quickly and be able to develop to the various demands of educational institution users (Azmi, 2019).

Indonesian language lessons as one of the subjects taught starting from basic education level, apart from being a source of other knowledge, are also a means of logical, analytical and systematic thinking. As a subject that is related to abstract concepts, in presenting the subject matter, lessons must be presented in a more interesting way and in accordance with the conditions and circumstances

of the students. This is of course intended so that in the learning process students are more active and motivated to learn. For this reason, there needs to be a special approach applied by the teacher.

Learning activities in class IV at SD Negeri 078553 Orlin in carrying out learning activities must be oriented towards student needs, one of which is choosing learning methods that can create a safe, comfortable and enjoyable learning atmosphere, such as through demonstration methods. Teachers often impose their will without paying attention to the needs, interests and talents of students. The weakness of our educators is that they never explore the potential and talents of students. Educators should pay attention to children's needs, not force something that makes students less comfortable in studying. For this reason, it is necessary to learn through understanding and doing, not just memorizing or remembering. It would be different if students were invited to observe, guess, act, try, and even be able to answer and debate, that way the process of learning Indonesian would be more meaningful.

It has now been widely discovered that the quality of learning will improve if students have ample opportunities to ask questions, discuss and actively use the new knowledge they have acquired. In this way it is also known that the new knowledge tends to be better understood, meaningful and mastered. In fact, students who are active and able to understand will be more able to think critically and creatively in dealing with existing problems.

Based on observations of students, there are several obstacles faced in the Indonesian language learning process, one of which is the students' lack of understanding of the material taught by the teacher. This condition is caused by various things, including: (1) students pay less attention to the material being presented because they feel bored with the monotonous learning model, which is dominated by the teacher, so that students become less active and learning outcomes fall below the predetermined KKM, (2) The teacher's way of teaching is boring, does not attract students' attention, (3) In the teaching and learning process so far it has only been limited to efforts to make students capable and skilled at working on the existing problems so that the learning that takes place is less meaningful and feels boring and students have difficulty making connections. material with everyday events. (4) a learning atmosphere that only faces the blackboard in front without using media so that learning seems stiff. (5) students' fear of conveying problems or ideas they have received because of the shadow of error. If this is allowed to continue, it will result in the learning objectives not being achieved as expected.

So far, students' low motivation to learn is mostly due to certain approaches, methods or strategies used by teachers in the learning process which are still traditional in nature, and do not provide opportunities for students to develop their thinking patterns according to their respective abilities. As a result, students' creativity and scientific thinking abilities cannot develop optimally. For this reason, teachers need to choose a teaching method or approach that can help develop students' thinking patterns.

Uno (2009) motivation greatly determines the quality of a person's behavior. A person's motivation to carry out something high or low is inferred from the quality of his behavior, which is shown by sincerity, perseverance, attention and fortitude. Motivation to learn is a psychological factor that is non-intellectual. Its very typical role is in terms of changing enthusiasm (passion), feeling happy and

enthusiastic about learning. Furthermore, Sardiman (1996: 75) stated that a person's learning intensity and motivation will greatly determine the level of learning achievement. Besides that, motivation is inspired by individual values that can be modified in learning activities.

The demonstration method is a way of teaching in which an instructor or team of teachers shows, shows a process (relevant to the subject matter or material being presented), so that all students in the class can see, observe, hear, perhaps grope, and feel the process. demonstrated by the teacher. The demonstration method is a teaching method by demonstrating items, events, rules and the sequence of carrying out an activity, either directly or through the use of media that is relevant to the subject matter or material being presented. Another understanding from experts regarding the meaning of the demonstration method is a way of presenting lessons by demonstrating or demonstrating to students a particular process, situation or object that is being studied, either actually or imitation, which is often accompanied by an oral explanation. The demonstration method is usually applied with drama, poetry, etc.

Based on the description above, the author tries to contribute to science learning through the use of demonstration methods which can be effective in facilitating Indonesian language learning at SD Negeri 078553 Orlin. Another reason for choosing the demonstration method is because this learning model is very interesting when applied to students. Students will be more active in learning on their own and finding out the parts assigned to them. So it can provide learning motivation to students and also make it easier to deliver learning material related to the lesson. From the explanation above, the author tries to take a research with the title "The Influence of the Demonstration Method on the Learning Motivation of Class VI Students at SDN 078553 Orlin, South Nias Regency in Indonesian Language Subjects".

Methods

The method used in this research is a descriptive qualitative method because through the results analyzed it can provide an overview of the problems being studied with the actual situation, namely the learning difficulties experienced by students in carrying out Indonesian language learning activities. One of the reasons for using qualitative research is because of the researcher's experience in understanding the learning characteristics of students who often experience obstacles in understanding the subject matter even though they have been given an in-depth understanding. The data analysis techniques are carried out through observation, interviews and documentation using primary and secondary data sources.

Table 1
Research Sample

Class	Gender		Amount
	Man	Woman	
VI	13 People	19 People	32 People

Source: Primary Data 2024

Determining the sample in this research was by using *sampling* with a *probability sampling technique*. The *probability sampling* technique is a sampling technique that assumes that each population has the same chance of being selected as a sample. One of the reasons for using probability

sampling techniques is because there is no sampling frame. In qualitative research, the research instrument or tool is the researcher himself. The instruments or tools in question from the beginning to the end of the research. Researchers themselves are active in the research carried out starting from determining the research focus, data sources, data analysis to conclusions. Apart from that, researchers also act as researchers themselves and evaluators. This research uses *human instruments*.

Results and Discussion

Learning motivation is an encouragement from within students to be involved in learning activities. Each student has different abilities so as a teacher you need to understand these characteristics. Learning methods are efforts made to overcome various student problems so that they are able to generate learning motivation and achieve learning outcomes. Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted, researchers obtained information that in carrying out learning activities it was known that students' motivation was very low to participate in learning activities so that involvement in learning activities was low. This problem is basically caused by internal factors of students and other external factors which cause students' learning concentration to be disturbed.

Internal factors are factors that come from within students and influence learning motivation. After conducting interviews with respondents, it was discovered that students had difficulty understanding the subjects because they tended to use the lecture method. Students are used as loyal listeners and teachers as the only source of learning. As a result, their involvement in learning activities is minimal, which influences low learning motivation. Meanwhile, externally, factors originating from outside such as the use of learning technology media are still limited, the methods used are monotonous and the learning environment for students. Positive energy can increase motivation and good learning outcomes, but on the other hand, if the condition of the students or teachers is not good then the learning motivation obtained will be low.

Table 2
Students' learning motivation at SDN 078553 Orlin

Indicator	Information		
	Low	Currently	Tall
There is curiosity about the learning material	√		
Provide arguments (suggestions, criticism)	√		
Pay attention to the teacher during the learning process		√	
Doing the job well		√	
Student learning outcomes	√		

Students have low learning motivation to participate in learning activities carried out by the teacher even though they have used the right media. It can be seen that they are enthusiastic about listening to learning activities and taking advantage of the opportunity to ask questions. The difficulty

in understanding the learning material greatly influences the learning outcomes obtained where students have very low scores. Teachers have an important role in carrying out diagnostics that cause students' learning difficulties so that they are able to provide learning evaluations with the aim of obtaining good results.

In this learning activity, diagnostics are carried out by providing an initial assessment to students and taking approaches both individually and in groups to determine the initial abilities possessed by the students themselves. Teachers provide direction or guidance to students to arouse their enthusiasm for learning and utilize existing media and methods that are oriented to students' needs, one of which is using the demonstration method. After applying the demonstration method, it is known that students have high learning motivation because they feel that the learning process carried out is in accordance with their initial abilities. Students are very enthusiastic about being involved in learning activities that involve their roles. In detail, the development of students' learning motivation can be seen in the following table :

Table 3
Motivation to learn after the demonstration method at SDN 078553 Orlin

Indicator	Information		
	Low	Currently	Tall
There is curiosity about the learning material			√
Provide arguments (suggestions, criticism)		√	
Pay attention to the teacher during the learning process			√
Doing the job well			√
Student learning outcomes			√

Based on the table above, it is known that on average students have high learning motivation to be involved in learning activities. In the indicator of giving arguments, students have done well, but the quality of the arguments given is still in the medium category and there are still few students who are able to carry out this indicator. However, if we look at the learning progress, it can be seen that the application of this demonstration method has a positive impact on students' learning motivation.

The demonstration method is very effective in learning activities because it gives students the opportunity to behave independently with guidance from the subject teacher. This is known from the involvement of students in demonstrating the learning material that has been directed by the teacher by showing the agreed attitude. Then, after reflecting on the learning activities, the students felt very happy with carrying out the learning activities through the implementation of the demonstration method and even hoped that the teacher would continue to apply this method. Students feel very involved in learning activities and have memorable learning experiences.

If observed in terms of time, the application of the demonstration method in the classroom does

not take a long time because the teacher has distributed the roles of each group with different themes. Before implementing this method, planning has been carried out from the start so that it helps teachers to control learning activities even though it requires extra energy.

Demonstration method is very important in teaching because it makes abstract concepts more concrete and easier for students to understand. Here are several reasons why the demonstration method has high urgency in teaching:

1. **Clarifying Abstract Concepts** : Concepts that are difficult to understand theoretically can become clear through direct demonstration. For example, physics principles such as force , motion, or pressure, become easier to understand when students can see them in action.
2. **Activating Learning** : Demonstrations engage students directly in the learning process. They can see, hear, and often participate in demonstrations, which helps improve information retention.
3. **Improves Memory** : The visual experience and hands-on practice of demonstrations help students to remember information better than just reading or listening.
4. **Reduces Fear and Distrust** : Demonstrations give students the opportunity to see that difficult concepts can actually be mastered and applied in everyday life. This can reduce their fear or distrust of certain subjects.
5. **Encourage Collaboration and Discussion** : Demonstrations often involve students in discussion and collaboration with fellow students and teachers. This creates an interactive learning environment and allows students to learn from each other .
6. **Enriching the Learning Experience** : By providing hands-on experience, demonstrations can be moments that enrich students' learning experiences, motivating them to engage more deeply with the subject matter.
7. **Enhance Practical Skills** : Especially in subjects such as science, mathematics, or the arts, demonstrations provide students with opportunities to develop practical skills, such as laboratory skills, problem-solving skills, or artistic skills.

Whereas Motivating students is one of the most important aspects of effective teaching. Here are some strategies to increase student motivation:

1. **Make Personal Connections** : Get to know each student's needs, interests, and personality. Give them personal attention and support, so they feel valued and connected to you as a teacher.
2. **Provide Clear Goals** : Set specific, measurable, and achievable goals for students. Help them understand why these goals are important and how achieving them can have a positive impact.

3. **Make Learning Interesting** : Use a variety of teaching methods, including demonstrations, discussions, games, or projects, to keep learning interesting and relevant for students.
4. **Provide Constructive Feedback** : Provide clear and in-depth feedback on student performance. Encourage them to see mistakes as learning opportunities and focus on their progress rather than just the end result.
5. **Provide Space for Creativity** : Give students the freedom to express their own ideas and find unique solutions to problems faced in learning.
6. **Provide Recognition and Praise** : Public appreciation of student achievements and their efforts. Recognition of their hard work and achievements can increase their self-confidence and motivation to continue learning.
7. **Create a Positive Learning Environment** : Create a supportive, safe, and inclusive environment in the classroom. Make sure that students feel comfortable to participate, express, and ask questions without fear of being judged.
8. **Make Connections between the Material and Real Life** : Demonstrate the relevance of the subject matter to the student's daily life or future career. This helps them see the value in the learning they receive.
9. **Provide Appropriate Challenges** : Provide assignments that are challenging but appropriate to the student's ability level. The right challenge can increase their motivation to learn and grow.
10. **Involve Students in Decision Making** : Provide students with opportunities to participate in the decision-making process related to classroom learning. This can give them a sense of responsibility and control over their learning process.

The new educational paradigm places more emphasis on students as humans who have the potential to learn and develop. Students must be active in the search and development of knowledge. The truth of science is not limited to what is conveyed by the teacher. Teachers must change their role, no longer as the highest scientific authority and indoctrination, but to become facilitators who guide students towards the formation of knowledge by themselves. Through this new paradigm, it is hoped that in class students will be active in learning, active in discussions, brave in conveying ideas and accepting ideas from others, creative in finding solutions to problems they face and having high self-confidence.

The rationale for learning Indonesian in primary and secondary education is emphasized so that students can systemize the material, information or abilities they already have about humans and their environment to become more meaningful, more sensitive and responsive to various social problems in a rational and responsible manner. Increase a sense of tolerance and brotherhood in one's own

environment and between people. Make students aware that current events are the result of past human behavior and that they have the ability to shape their own future. Emphasizes the need for reading, writing and observation.

However, on the other hand, learning Indonesian in the field still appears to have many shortcomings. Learning Indonesian in elementary schools ignores ideas and does not develop students' potential optimally. Learning Indonesian is just memorizing so that it is achieved in accordance with the applicable curriculum. Teachers are trapped in monotonous, static lecture teaching methods, without using other varied methods. This is an obstacle or obstacle faced by Indonesian language teachers . As a result, student activity and potential development in learning is low and does not reach optimal levels. So that Indonesian language learning can achieve its goals optimally, teachers strive to improve the quality of education starting from the role of the teacher as a leader and who will take students to their destination. Through learning activities, a teacher needs to choose interesting learning strategies

Conclusion

The learning methods applied by teachers in the learning process have a very important role in generating students' learning motivation, one of which is in class VI of SD Negeri 078553 Orlin which applies the demonstration method. This method has succeeded in generating motivation in students because they are given full involvement in demonstrating the theory of the subject concerned. Thus creating safe, comfortable and enjoyable learning as well as student involvement, known as learning that supports students' needs. Based on the results of observations, the researcher concluded that the demonstration method was effective for application at the elementary school education level. Through this research, it is hoped that it can become a reference for all parties to implement learning methods that are pro-student

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